

RETICULARIA DUDKAE. A NEW MYXOMYCETE SPECIES FROM OAK FORESTS OF EASTERN UKRAINE

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Summary. LEONTYEV D.V. & G. MORENO (2011). *Reticularia dudkae*. A new myxomycete species from oak forests of Eastern Ukraine. *Bol. Soc. Micol. Madrid* 35: 85-94.

Based on material collected in *Quercus robur* communities of Gomolsha Forest National Park (Ukraine), the new species *Reticularia dudkae* is described, characterized by typical pseudoaethalia, composed of clearly spherical sporothecae. Additional characters of the species are: the unique ornamentation of the inner peridial surface, membranous and iridescent peridia of the sporothecae, the absence of a white rim surrounding the base of the pseudoaethalia and reticulate spores lacking a smooth area. The above mentioned diagnostic features are included in a modified key of the genus *Reticularia*.

Key words: *Protozoa*, *Reticulariaceae*, slime moulds, aethalium, pseudoaethalium, inner peridium ultrastructure.

Resumen. LEONTYEV D.V. & G. MORENO (2011). *Reticularia dudkae*. Una nueva especie de mixomicete de los bosques de roble del este de Ucrania. *Bol. Soc. Micol. Madrid* 35: 85-94.

Basado en el material recogido en las comunidades de *Quercus robur* del Parque Nacional de Gomolsha Forest (Ucrania), se describe la nueva especie *Reticularia dudkae*, que se caracteriza por su típico pseudoaetelio, formado por una esporoteca esférica. Otros caracteres de las especies son: la ornamentación única de la superficie interna del peridio, la cubierta membranosa e iridiscente de la esporoteca, la ausencia de borde blanco alrededor del pseudoaetelio y las esporas reticuladas sin superficie lisa. Las características mencionadas de diagnóstico se incluyen en una clave de identificación del género *Reticularia*.

Palabras clave: *Protozoa*, *Reticulariaceae*, hongos mucilaginosos, etelio, pseudoaetelio, ultraestructura del peridio interno.

INTRODUCTION

The myxomycete genera *Reticularia* Bull. and *Tubifera* G.F. Gmel. are known as closely related taxa within the family *Reticulariaceae* Chevall. (FIORE-DONNO *et al.*, 2005, 2008). The difference between them seems to be absolutely clear: *Reticularia* forms a true aethalium while *Tubifera* has pseudoaethalia

consisting of cylindrical sporothecae. One may assume that fructifications of *Reticularia* originated from pseudoaethalia, resembling those of *Tubifera*, by integration and reduction of cylindrical sporothecae. However, those species of *Reticularia*, which have an “Enteridium”-type structure (*R. splendens* Morgan, *R. jurana* Meyl.), have a clearly spherical shape of the spore-holding spaces between pseudocapillitium plates

[See, for example, the pictures in MARTIN & ALEXOPULOS (1969)]. It means that supposed ancestor of “Enteridium”-type *Reticularia* should have a pseudoaethalium, consisting of spherical sporothecae. Unfortunately, no species of *Reticulariaceae* with such a fruiting body structure has been described. Only one species, *Tubifera dimorphoteca* Nann.-Bremek. & Loer, forms two types of sporothecae: large cylindrical ones at the top of fructification and small spherical ones in the surface of its hypothallic “stalk”. Of course, this species is not a suitable candidate for ancestors of *Reticularia*.

All of these would remain just as a hypothesis if we had not collected a series of specimens with such “ancestral” features: these are typical pseudoaethalia, composed of only spherical sporothecae. The unique ornamentation of the inner peridial surface, which does not correspond to any known member of the *Reticulariaceae*, convinced us of the species novelty of this material. Moreover, such a fructification structure corresponds neither to *Tubifera* (because of the sporothecae shape) nor to *Reticularia* (because of the fructification type), and formally should be considered as a new genus. But, taking into account the obvious similarity of collected specimens with “Enteridium”-type *Reticularia*, we describe it here as a new species of the latter genus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material of the study consists of 7 specimens of the new species, collected in summer seasons of 2003–2006 in the Gomolsha Forests National Nature Park (Ukraine). In addition, 11 specimens of *Reticularia splendens* and 3 specimens of *R. jurana* collected in different areas of Ukraine and the Russian Federation were used for comparison. We also used the data for 45 specimens of *Tubifera ferruginosa* (Batsch) J.F. Gmel., obtained in other investigations (LEONTYEV & FEFELOV, 2009). Type material of the new species is deposited in the herbarium of the V.N. Karasin National University of Kharkiv, Ukraine (CWU); duplicates were sent to the National Herbarium of Ukraine (KW) and the Herbarium

of the University of Alcalá de Henares, Spain (AH).

Examination of the specimens was carried out using a light microscope (LM) Biolam P-15 (with oil immersion) and the scanning electron microscope (SEM) Jeol JSM-6060 and Zeiss DSM-950 (30 kV, gold evaporation), images were prepared using critical point drying (CASTILLO & *al.*, 1997). Pseudoaethalia were measured with a millimetre ruler, and spore size was measured by ocular micrometer under oil immersion. Thirty spores were measured for each specimen to estimate the range of variation.

Methods of descriptive statistics, namely calculation of means, standard deviations and standard errors were used to describe the morphological variety of species. The range of spore size is given for all species as “lower quartile – upper quartile”. All calculations were executed using StatSoft Statistica 6.0, and Microsoft Excel 2003 software.

RESULTS

The new species, *Reticularia dudkae*, is characterized by the shining rust-brown pillow-like pseudoaethalia, consisting of spherical sporothecae with complete or almost complete peridial cover. The most important ultrastructural feature is the wave-like embossments on the internal surface of the peridium. The diagnosis of the new species is provided below.

***Reticularia dudkae* Leontyev & G. Moreno, sp. nov. (Figs 1-2).**

MycoBank MB 561707.

Etymology: named in honor of Prof. Irina O. Dudka, who initiated a SEM study of *Reticularia* in Ukraine.

Latin Diagnosis: *Pseudoaethalia singularia*, 22-27 mm longa, 20-22 mm lata, 8-12 mm alta, pulvinata, desuper rotunda vel subovoidea, hemisphaerica, saturo rufobrunnea. Sporothecae sphaericae vel ovoideae, (0.1-)0.4-0.6(-1.0) mm diam., cum peridium perpetuum. Dorsum

Fig. 1. *Reticularia dudkae* Leontyev & G. Moreno

a. General view of a pseudoaethalium; b. Surface of the pseudoaethalium from above, with the outer part of individual sporothecae apparent; c. Broken sporothecae, observed when the cortical part of pseudoaethalium is peeled away; d. Isolated individual sporothecae, showing a zone with a perforation; e. Peridium of sporothecae as seen with LM, showing an area where individual sporothecae lose their individuality, forming a pseudocapillitium; f. Spores from above and in optical section, with apparent oil droplets.

pseudoaethaliorum bullatum, sporothecarum partium superium compingent, cum assae laminae mucosae inter sporothecae. Peridium laeve, subtranslucidum, lucem brunneolae, nitidum et iridis. Peridium interno undarum ornatum. Pseudocapillitium absunt vel sporothaecae peridii formatum, laminoideum, perforatum, raro filamentosum. Hypothallus non multus, spongiosus, sine orbe albo. Sporae per saturam rufobrunneae, lucem brunneolae, (6.0-)6.8-7.5(-8.2) μ m diam., reticulatae, sine area laevi. Plasmodium ignotum. In sylvis deciduis, frequento querceta, in lignis consumptis.

Pseudoaethalia solitary, 22-27 mm long, 20-22

mm wide, 8-12 mm tall, pulvinate, rounded as seen from above, saturated rust-brown. *Individual sporothecae* spherical or short ovoid, (0.1-)0.4-0.6(-1.0) mm in diam., completely covered by peridium. *Surface of pseudoaethalium* bullate, formed by individual sporothecae with dried slime bands between them. *Peridium* smooth, translucent, shining and somewhat iridescent, yellowish-brown in transmitted light. *Internal surface of peridium* consists of convex rounded plates, surrounded by wave-like folds (seen in SEM). *Pseudocapillitium* absent; in the central part of the pseudoaethalium some individual sporothecae lose their individuality and their

Fig. 2. *Reticularia dudkae* Leontyev & G. Moreno, CWU-M2752

a. General view of pseudoaethalia; b-c. Surface of the pseudoaethalium as observed from above, outer part of individual sporothecae apparent (LM and SEM); d-e. Broken sporothecae, as observed when cortical part of pseudoaethalium is peeled away (LM and SEM); f. Cross section of a pseudoaethalium, showing the spherical sporothecae; g. Isolated individual sporothecae; h. Peridium of well developed sporothecae; i. Peridium of confluent sporothecae, showing perforated plates of the pseudocapillitium.

peridia form a pseudocapillitium consist of perforated plates and, rarely, bands. *Hypothallus* spongy, sparse, with no white rim around the base of pseudoaethalium. *Spores* in mass rust-brown, brownish in transmitted light, (6.0-)6.8-7.5(-8.2) µm diam., covered with a fine reticulum with no smooth area. *Plasmodium* not seen. *Ecology*: in deciduous forests with a prevalence of *Quercus robur*, on decomposed wood.

Holotypus: Ukraine, Kharkiv region, Gomolsha Forests National Nature Park, 49°37'37"N

36°19'38"E (Zayachiy ravine, oak forest with the addition of ash and lime trees), CWU-M2752 (referred before as CWU MR-40). 1-VII-2003, three pseudoaethalia on the wood of fallen trunk of *Quercus robur* L., leg. D.V. Leontyev.

Other collections. All examined specimens are collected in the Gomolsha Forests, situated in the East Forest-Steppe region of Ukraine. CWU-M2753: 17-VII-2004, aethalium on the wood of fallen trunk of *Fraxinus excelsior* L. (?), leg. D.V.

Fig. 3. Internal structure of fructification in *Tubifera* and *Reticularia* (schematically)

a-b. Cylindrical sporothecae: a. *Tubifera ferruginosa*, b. *Reticularia lycoperdon*; c-d. Sphaerical sporothecae: c. *R. dudkae*. d. *R. splendens*.

Leontyev; CWU-M2757: 2-VII-2006, aethalium on the wood of fallen trunk of *Q. robur*, leg. D.V. Leontyev; CWU-M2758: 24-VII-2006, aethalium on the wood of fallen trunk of *Tilia cordata* L., leg. D.V. Leontyev.

DISCUSSION

Fructification structure. As we stated above, *Reticularia dudkae* does not correspond formally to any genus of Myxomycetes, because typical pseudoaethalia, composed of only spherical sporothecae, are not known among *Reticulariaceae*. However, it is obviously related to *Tubifera* and *Reticularia*, having rust-coloured spore mass, membranous peridium, no true capillitium and clearly reticulate spores.

The place, occupied by *R. dudkae* in the evolution of these two genera, seems to be quite

unique (Fig. 3). There exist at least two paths of morphological evolution within the *Tubifera-Reticularia* complex: species with spherical and cylindrical sporothecae. In the first path, a separate sporothecae, forming pseudoaethalium, are characteristic of *Tubifera* spp (Fig. 3a), and confluent ones, are probably displayed by *Reticularia lycoperdon* Bull. and other species with branching pseudocapillitium with few anastomoses (Fig. 3b). As for the second path, confluent spherical sporothecae are displayed by “Enteridium” species: *R. splendens* and *R. jurana* (Fig. 3d), and separate ones, forming pseudoaethalia, are, as far as we know, displayed only by *R. dudkae* (Fig. 3c).

Reticularia splendens is especially close to *R. dudkae*. Besides very similar internal structure, a close relationship between these two species is suggested by the similar size and proportions

Fig. 4. Internal surface of peridium in *Reticularia dudkae*, showing characteristic ornamentation.

of fructifications, texture of cortex, size and ornamentation of spores (see below).

Taking into account all these similarities, we place the new species in the genus *Reticularia*, despite its unusual pseudoaethalial structure.

Peridial ultrastructure. The criterion of inner peridial surface ultrastructure was introduced in taxonomy of the *Reticulariaceae* in 1982, when R.K. Nelson, R.W. Scheetz and C.J. Alexopoulos showed that *Tubifera microsperma* Berk. & M.A. Curtis. has a very peculiar ornamentation, the need to look like “rimmed craters”. In contrast, the similar species *T. arachnoidea* was shown to have a completely smooth peridial surface, and *T. casparyi* Rostaf. – a granular peridium with scattered “craters” (NELSON *et al.*, 1982). In 2009 an annular ornamentation of the inner peridial surface was observed in *T. applanata* Leontyev & Fefelov and a granulate surface – in *T. dictyoderma* Nann.-Bremek. & Loer (LEONTYEV & FEFELOV, 2009).

Such diversity of peridial ultrastructure in *Tubifera* suggests looking for individual peculiarities of the inner ornamentation in related genera, namely in *Reticularia*. The idea proved its value since a SEM-study of the type specimen of *Reticularia dudkae* demonstrated the unique ornamentation of its internal peridial surface. It consists of convex rounded plates, surrounded by

wave-like folds (Fig. 4a). The peridium of *Reticularia dudkae* looks from inside like a surface of soft clay, covered with numerous fingerprints. As far as we know, such ornamentation is not yet described for any species of *Reticularia*. It is also unknown in any *Tubifera* species, supporting a supposition that *R. dudkae* has nothing in common with *Tubifera ferruginosa*, although some superficial similarity may be observed.

Generally speaking, circular structures on the peridium are not unique for *Tubifera* spp. and *Reticularia dudkae*. Such ornamentation is known in myxomycetes of some other genera, including *Lycogala conicum* Pers. (NEUBERT *et al.*, 2003), *L. epidendrum* (L.) Fr. (MCHUGH & REID, 2008), *Dianema corticatum* Lister, *D. depressum* (Lister) Lister and *Perichaena luteola* (Kowalski) Gilert (RAMMELOO, 1983). It looks reasonable that members of *Dianemataceae* T. Macbr. appear in this list: the affinity of *Reticulariaceae* and *Dianemataceae* was supported by a DNA sequence analysis (FIORE-DONNO *et al.*, 2008).

In 2008 R. McHugh and C. Reid showed that circular embossments on the peridium of *Lycogala epidendrum* are caused by traces of a process of active water evacuation from maturing fruit body (MCHUGH & REID, 2008). However, there is no evidence, that the “fingerprint” ornamentation of *R. dudkae* has the similar origin.

Cortex. The surface of the pseudoaethalium in

Fig. 5. Spores of *Reticularia* species (scale bar 1 µm)
 a-b. *R. dudkae*; c-d. *R. jurana*; e-g. *R. splendens*. Arrows indicate the splitted border of reticulation.

Reticularia dudkae is formed by upper parts of individual sporothecae; there is no solid smooth cortex, characteristic of other *Reticularia* species. Such a structure gives the new species a superficial similarity to *Tubifera*, being a possible source of confusion. However, in other *Reticularia* species, namely *R. jurana* and *R. splendens*, a bullate structure of the cortex is quite usual (MARTIN & ALEXOPULOS, 1969; KELLER & BROWN, 1999; NEUBERT *et al.*, 2003), being considered as a relict of pseudoaethalial structure of a fructification (LISTER, 1925). The difference between the abovementioned species and *R. dudkae* lies in the fact that the latter shows intact sporothecal structure not only outside, but also inside.

The cortex of a *Reticularia dudkae* pseudoaethalium may be peeled away as the whole cover (Fig. 1a, c) with some individual sporothecae hav-

ing been broken in the process. In our experience, no species of *Tubifera* may be “stripped” in this way. Probably, the dried slime cover, forming bands between sporothecae tips, integrates the cortex of the pseudoaethalium.

Spores. Spores of *Reticularia dudkae* are covered with a complete reticulation consisting of angular meshes, 6-8 across the spore diameter (Fig. 5a-b). Quite characteristic is the absence of a smooth area, typical for *Reticularia jurana*, *R. splendens* and other *Reticularia* species (LISTER, 1925; MARTIN & ALEXOPULOS, 1969; NEUBERT *et al.*, 2003). SEM studies of spore ornamentation have shown that borders of meshes in *Reticularia jurana* and *R. splendens* are split into several layers, especially in sites of borders cross (Fig. 5f). However, in *Reticularia dudkae*, the borders of meshes are mainly entire,

Species	Specimens measured	Spores measured for each specimen	Mean (μm)	Standard errors	Standard deviations
<i>Reticularia dudkae</i>	7	30	7.058	0.073	0.567
<i>R. jurana</i>	3	30	7.192	0.062	0.483
<i>R. splendens</i>	11	30	7.252	0.065	0.621
<i>Tubifera ferruginosa</i>	45	30	6.430	0.029	0.572

Table 1. Spore size of investigated specimens of *Reticularia* and *Tubifera*.

Fig. 6. Spore size range in *Reticularia* and *Tubifera* species
Lines show standard deviations, boxes-standard errors of mean.

with no splitting.

Measurements show no difference between spore size in *Reticularia dudkae*, *R. jurana* and *R. splendens*. In contrast, *Tubifera ferruginosa* has a significantly ($p < 0.05$) smaller spores than all other studied *Reticularia* species (Tab.1; Fig. 6).

Similarity with other species. Although the general appearance of *Reticularia dudkae* is quite characteristic, it may be confused with some other species of *Reticulariaceae*.

Reticularia splendens is probably the closest species to *R. dudkae*. However, it differs from the latter by the absence of intact sporothecae, dull and rough cortex and pseudocapillitium, smooth

area on spores, white hypothallic ring around the aethalium and, finally, by the absence of wave-like ornamentation on the inner surface of the peridium.

Reticularia lobata has very small spherical aethalia, gathered in dense groups, which may be confused with pseudoaethalia. Because *Reticularia dudkae* has a pseudoaethalium, consisting of spherical sporothecae, it is morphologically similar to *R. lobata*. Nevertheless, the general appearance of the two species is totally different. All available pictures of *R. lobata* (LISTER, 1925; MARTIN & ALEXOPULOS, 1969; NANNENGA-BREMEKAMP, 1991) show small flat groups of rounded aethalia, which are not heaped on each other. One another difference is the absence of pseudocapillitial threads inside sporothecae of *R. dudkae* and their presence in *R. lobata*. It means that spherical spore-containing structures are clearly sporothecae, not aethalia, and that the total fructification is a typical pseudoaethalium, not a “pseudoaethalium consisting of aethalia”, as in *R. lobata*¹. Finally, *R. lobata* has a dull peridium, brown spore mass and spores

¹ Actually, there is no evidence, that the ‘pseudocapillitium’ of *R. lobata* is not a true capillitium. As far as we know, nobody has proved, that ‘aethalia’ of *R. lobata* are formed by the confluence of more primitive spore-holding structures. It means, that the ‘aethalia’ of *R. lobata* may appear to be ordinary sporothecae, and the ‘group of aethalia’ – a primitive pseudoaethalium. As for the well known absence of capillitium in *Liceales*, this principle looks to be somewhat dogmatic. True capillitium is known at least in *Tubifera* (Nannenga-Bremekamp, 1991).

with a smooth area while *R. dudkae* has a shining membranous peridium, rust-coloured spore mass and no smooth area on the spores.

Tubifera ferruginosa is similar with *Reticularia dudkae* with its pseudoaethalial structure, shining membranous peridium and spores which often have no smooth area. The principal difference between these two species is the shape of the sporothecae: in *T. ferruginosa* they are cylin-

drical, reaching simultaneously both the base and the top of the fructification. The pseudoaethalium of *R. dudkae* consists of spherical sporothecae, most of which are submerged within its mass, reaching and the top of the fructification. Other important characters are spore size (6.8-7.5 µm in *R. dudkae*, 5.8-6.8 in *T. ferruginosa*) and the inner peridial surface.

**KEY TO THE GENUS *RETICULARIA*
INCLUDING PSEUDOAEETHALIOID
SPECIES OF *LICEALES***

- 1 Spore mass rust-brown or yellowish, spores reticulate 2
 1* Spore mass olive-brown or chestnut-brown, spores spiny or verrucose
 *Reticularia olivacea*, *R. rubiginosa*, *R. simulans*, *Lindbladia tubulina*² (not considered here)
 2 Fructifications pseudoaethalia; individual sporothecae are well developed, not strongly confluent....
 3
 2* Fructifications aethalia; individual sporothecae are confluent, forming a pseudocapillitium..... 4
 3 Sporothecae mainly cylindrical, extending from the base up to the surface of the fructification
 genus *Tubifera* (not considered here)
 3* Sporothecae mainly spherical, only a few reaching the surface of the fructification *R. dudkae*
 4 Fructifications small, 0.5-5 mm diam. 5
 4* Fructifications large, 1-10 cm diam. 7
 5 Fructifications and spores bright yellow *R. aurea*
 5* Fructifications and spores brown or purple-brown 6
 6 Fructifications globose, 0.5-1 mm diam., spores 7-8 µm *R. lobata*
 6* Fructifications vermicular, 1 mm diam., up to 10 mm long, spores 10-12 µm *R. liceoides*
 7 Cortex white or greyish, often silvery shining *R. lycoperdon*
 7* Cortex not as above 8
 8 Pseudocapillitium thin, thread-like 9
 8* Pseudocapillitium consist of perforated plates, forming a rigid three-dimensional net with rounded
 meshes 10
 9 Pseudocapillitial threads not flattened, dichotomously branched *R. intermedia*
 9* Pseudocapillitial threads flattened, anastomosing to form a dense net *R. jurana*
 10 Cortex smooth or rough and even slightly bullate, dull, hypothallus form a white rim around
 aethalium, spores with a smooth area *R. splendens*
 10* Cortex clearly bullate, shining, hypothallus not forming a white rim, spores with no smooth area
 (*R. dudkae*)

² It is highly probable, that olive-coloured *Reticularia* species are much more related to *Lindbladia*, than to other *Reticulariaceae*, but this subject needs a special investigation.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- CASTILLO, A., G. MORENO, C. ILLANA & J. LAGO (1997). A critical study of some *Stemonitales*. *Mycol. Res.* 101: 1329-1340.
- FIORE-DONNO A.M., C. BERNEY, J. PAWLOWSKI & S.L. BALDAUF (2005). Higher-order phylogeny of plasmodial slime molds (*Myxogastria*) based on EF1A and SSU rRNA sequences. *J. Euk. Microbiol.* 52: 201-210.
- FIORE-DONNO A.M., J. PAWLOWSKI & T. CAVALIER-SMITH (2008). Phylogenetic relationships in *Trichiales* and *Liceales*. Abstracts of 6th International congress on the Systematics and Ecology of *Myxomycetes*. Yalta, p.27.
- KELLER H.W. & K.L. BROWN (1999). *Myxomycetes of Ohio: their Systematics, Biology and Use in Teaching*. Columbus, Ohio. Ohio Biological Survey.
- LEONTYEV, D.V. & K.A. FEFELOV (2009). *Tubulifera applanata*. The new species from Eastern Europe and Northern Asia. *Bol. Soc. Micol. Madrid* 33: 115-127.
- LISTER, A. (1925). *Monograph of the Mycetozoa* (3rd. ed.). London. Brit. Mus.
- MARTIN, G.W. & C.J. ALEXOPOULOS (1969). *The Myxomycetes*. Iowa City. Iowa Univ. Press.
- MCHUGH R. & C. REID (2008). Aethalium cortex formation in the Myxomycete *Lycogala terrestre*. *Rev. Mexicana Micol.* 27: 53-57.
- NANNENGA-BREMEKAMP, N.E. (1991). *A Guide to Temperate Myxomycetes*. Bristol: Biopress Ltd.
- NELSON, R.K., R.W. SCHEETZ & C.J. ALEXOPOULOS (1982). Taxonomic studies in the myxomycetes. V. Significance of peridial and spore ornamentations in the genus *Tubifera*, with a revised key to the species. *Mycologia* 74: 541-548.
- NEUBERT, H, W. NOWOTNY & K. BAUMANN (1993). *Die Myxomyceten Deutschlands und des angrenzenden Alpenraumes unter besonderer Berücksichtigung Österreichs*. Gomaringen. Baumann. Bd. 1.
- RAMMELOO J., ed. (1983). *Icones Mycologicae*. Jardin Botanique National de Belgique. Pl. 19-34.